

The Issue Of Choosing Educational Material For Literature Classes

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Abstract: *In the article, it is written about what standards are followed when choosing material for literature classes and determining its content, so that the lesson will be well organized. Also, questions and assignments are given the role and importance of studying the work. It has been studied that by improving them, it is possible to increase the quality of education and interest the student.*

Keywords — choosing material, literature, lesson, questions, assignments, education, interest, student.

INTRODUCTION.

When choosing material for literature classes, defining its content, the following standards are followed:

1. The artistic height of the work.
2. Diversity in style and genre.
3. Appropriateness of the student's age.
4. Aspects of the work's ability to be mastered by the student.

When choosing material from modern Uzbek literature, it is necessary to pay serious attention to how deeply the spirit of the nation is reflected in the works. The national spirit of the people is mostly reflected in his works. Recommendation of texts of different complexity at each stage of education ensures moral enrichment and spiritual development of students. Also, it should not be forgotten that the teaching process should be ahead of the student's development. Let each student achieve it through certain difficulties. It is absolutely impossible to allow the educational process to adapt to the slow development of the student. That's when the student is interested and strives [10; p.5].

Literary and artistic materials recommended for learning are gradually becoming more complex, taking into account the student's age characteristics, interests and psychology. Art work forms and expands the student's reading skills, reveals new aspects of his inner world, has a significant impact on the process of formation of moral perfection in accordance with the requirements of literary education.

Different principles of didactics can be harmoniously used when placing examples of Uzbek literature in "Literature" textbooks of primary school. When determining the content of the Uzbek literature course for upper grades, the main thing is to maintain aesthetic and scientific priority in the given literary and artistic materials, to consider the age characteristics and interests of upper grade students, to determine the high point of the student's activity and to implement teaching based on these. There are scientific-journalistic, scientific-popular and autobiographical materials for studying the biographies and works of modern literary figures. Giving the opinions of great people about the personality of writers, giving their attitude to

the works of writers in the form of an epigraph or an epilogue also has a special educational value.

Professor M. While researching the formation and improvement of literary analysis skills in students, Mirkosimova emphasizes the difference between the analysis in the lower class and the analysis in the upper classes: "Students focus on expressive reading of the text, mastering its content, and developing oral speech. The teacher pays more attention to listening to the student's impressions. They help him understand the consequences of the events described in the work, pay special attention to spiritual education" [4; p. 23].

The scientist says that the following results can be achieved in literature lessons with a properly chosen method of analysis: instilling theoretical knowledge necessary for analysis; to educate the spiritual world of students by means of literary analysis, to develop emotional and logical thinking skills; improvement of outlook; as a result of gradually strengthening the necessary practical skills from the bottom up, sending them to independent creative work; create a clear understanding of the requirements and laws of artistic creation; to increase the reading level of students, to educate their aesthetic taste, to achieve formation as an active creative member of society; formation of speech culture, development of creative qualities, teaching to approach the artistic word with responsibility and love; with the help of the analysis of the works of different styles created in different periods, it is to educate a sense of respect for our rich literary heritage, to create a sense of pride in it, to give knowledge about the artists who deserve the attention of our people, and the artistic value of the works they created" [4; p. 52]. In the in-depth study of literature, the provision of literary-theoretical concepts in textbooks is of great importance. In this sense, methodically correct organization of their assimilation is also of particular importance. The science of literature teaching methodology assumes that several conditions must be fulfilled for this.

It is appropriate to provide complete information about many literary genres and literary-theoretical concepts characteristic of Uzbek classical and modern literature in textbooks before the work of this genre. After the reader has a complete idea of the genre, working on the analysis of the work is the guarantee of his success in this regard. The purpose of the study of literary and theoretical concepts typical of Uzbek classic literature is to form the ability of the student to use

special literary terms when analyzing a work of art. Without it, literature lessons will resemble a dry retelling of the content of the text.

A certain lexical basis is necessary for artistic and theoretical analysis of literary works. Effective acquisition of theoretical information at the lower levels of general secondary education increases the student's speech and theoretical activity. In grades 8-9, it facilitates the assimilation of literary and theoretical information at the next stages of education.

During the educational analysis of artistic works in literature classes, it is necessary to pay special attention to the author's lexicon aimed at revealing the personality of the characters of the work. Because this lexicon serves as a signal for students to the moral and aesthetic aspects reflected in the work of art. Deep mastering of such a lexicon with the help of theoretical knowledge, deep understanding of the human aspects inherent in the character of heroes leaves an indelible mark on their spirituality. Such theoretical knowledge leads to the formation of such skills as: correctly mastering and using terms, understanding the lexical meaning of a word, studying its grammatical significance and remembering it.

Another important factor that ensures the complete mastery of artistic texts by the student in literature classes is the questions and tasks prepared on their content. In the "Literature" textbooks, special questions and assignments are prepared for the analysis of general topics, biographies, and works. They also include questions that cover the concepts of theoretical information. In the process of getting acquainted with a number of textbooks, we were convinced that the questions and tasks created on the basis of literary texts are aimed only at retelling the content of the text. It is aimed at developing the student's oral speech. Too many questions are structured in such a way that the student does not think about the question or try to understand it fully. Finds the exact word-for-word answer to the question in the text and writes it down or gives the answer to the teacher. It is unlikely to form the student's spirituality with such activities, and everyday life shows the proof of this.

In addition to the above, it is appropriate to include in "Literature" textbooks a group of questions and tasks that reveal the artistic charm, value, and impact aspects of the work to be studied, the image of the characters' personalities, mental experiences and feelings, and show the national spirit reflected in the work.

Professor Q. Yoldoshev focused on questions and tasks: "Updated literary education requires that questions and tasks take a large place in "Literature" textbooks. Because the more the text-based questions in the textbooks serve to reveal the essence of the fiction, the more the children are directed to feel the appeal of the text, the more the goal of studying the literary work will be fully realized," says [7; p. 148]. Professor S. Matjonov says: "Questions given in textbooks serve to identify, generalize, deepen and strengthen knowledge, evaluate the expressed concepts, thus forming creative thinking skills and competencies in students", and "Reading book" published in 1971-1993 ", "Soviet Uzbek Literature",

"Motherland Literature", "Uzbek Literature" classifies the questions and assignments as follows:

1. Questions and assignments to determine the content of the text.
2. Questions and tasks aimed at studying the semantic connection between parts of the text, determining the author's point of view on the issues described in the text, and critically evaluating the cited examples.
3. Questions about studying the text externally (superficially)" [3; p. 106].

Regarding the definition of the content of "Literature" textbooks, it should be said that they should include the study of literature in connection with the subjects of mother tongue, history, music, visual arts and geography, as well as tasks and questions that ensure the implementation of intersubject communication issues.

Taking into account the importance of questions and tasks in understanding the meaning of the text, he believes that it is necessary to pay special attention to the creation of questions and tasks that teach students to think creatively in the processing of "Uzbek literature" textbooks, and in order to do this:

- 1) mastering the content of the text from an aesthetic and educational point of view;
- 2) determine the author's point of view on the issues covered in the text;
- 3) to study the causal connection between the events expressed in the text;
- 4) determining the relationship between the works of one author or the same theme;
- 5) believes that it is necessary to focus on cases such as critical evaluation of ideas and examples mentioned in the text [3; p. 145].

The scientist notes that he studied the questions in the textbooks of grades 5-8, divided into four groups according to the essence of the content:

1. Questions and tasks related to studying the ideological and artistic features of the works and mastering their general content.
2. Questions and assignments to strengthen the learned literary and theoretical concepts.
3. Questions and assignments on mastering the given information on the life and creative activity of writers.
4. Questions and assignments to determine students' attitude to life on the example of the events of the work.

In the work, the psychological features of the questions and tasks are discussed and it is said that the questions and tasks should be created based on the age characteristics of the students. For example, "due to the lack of life experience of the students of grades 5-7, they are only interested in the general

direction of the events of the work, reading, retelling, memorizing the literary text, the places related to the topic being studied, including the author's personal attitude to the events and characters described in the work, one character to another character. It is necessary to determine the assessment, to recommend questions and tasks to determine the relationship between the external portrait of the heroes, the image of nature and the inner spiritual world" [3; p. 145].

Methodist Q. Husanboeva believes that "any question of the teacher, whether it is rhetorical or requires a direct answer from students, increases the mental activity of the child" [8; p. 126]. "With the help of rhetorical questions, emphasis is placed on the important aspects of the studied material. It is possible to better see what is important and restore the connection between what was previously learned and the newly acquired knowledge. In this way, attention is paid to the careful assimilation of further information. Rhetorical questions strain the minds of students, strengthen their attention, prepare them to make generalizations and draw conclusions based on relatively stronger mental activity - independent thinking. Questions that require an answer, which are a continuation of this activity, train the student to clarify and prove the necessary facts, as well as to express his opinions independently," says [8; p. 129]. Professor S. Matjonov's group of questions and assignments in textbooks of grades 5-8 was improved according to the content, and the most important one - "questions and assignments that encourage the student to study independently" was added in this dissertation.

Also, types of questions and tasks are recommended according to their form. "If you were: ...", "when the hero of one work is replaced by the hero of another work", "...explain the genre characteristics of the work", "count the works of...", "the unique character of the author in the works of... show the features"-style questions and tasks that create a problem situation, encourage research, strengthen theoretical information, and show the uniqueness of the writer's life and work. Later, he compares independent characters. A skill becomes a skill

Types of questions and tasks according to their form:

1. Creates a problematic situation ("If you were:...")
2. Encouraging research ("when the hero of one work is replaced by the hero of another work").
3. Regarding theoretical information ("...explain the genre features of the work").
4. About the writer's life and work ("List the works of...", "Show the unique character traits of the author in the works of...").

Q. Husanboeva is a supporter of setting difficult tasks for students in literature classes. According to him: "setting complex educational tasks throws the student out of balance. Stimulates thinking and memory to work actively. Putting the student in a difficult situation with questions can be used when it is intended to discover or find something new. In the process of independently searching for an answer to the teacher's question, the students experience certain difficulties and have

some difficulties. By organizing complex situations, the teacher increases the knowledge and intellectual activity of students, helps them to master the phenomenon in depth, enriches their experience, and helps them to solve complex problems independently. Creating such an extraordinary educational situation, that is, surprising the child with a question, causes a strong feeling in the student, as it contradicts his previous ideas. And wonder is the beginning of understanding and the way to knowledge" [8; p. 130].

It is understood from this that, with the help of questions, students are responsible for solving the complex and complicated situations described in the works of art presented for learning in the textbooks, which is the guarantee of their maturity.

R. In Niyozmetova's doctoral dissertation, in the methodological structure of the "Uzbek language" textbooks, the study of literary materials was introduced based on the methodology related to reading academic texts of the type of scientific articles, questions and assignments were also aimed at this. These are far from literary readings.

The scientist, who touched on questions and tasks, describes them as: "a task, a creative problematic question, a key that determines the nature of the activity on the way of independent, goal-seeking" [5; p. 52]. He divides the questions and assignments into two types according to their location in relation to the text: 1. Assignments given before reading the literary text; 2. Questions and assignments after getting acquainted with literary education. Since the goal of the scientific work is to study Uzbek literature in Russian groups, the author concludes that the questions and assignments should create a suitable speech situation for the comfortable communication in the Uzbek language. R. Niyozmetova envisages three types of preparation according to the method of completing questions and assignments: 1. Questions and assignments intended for all students in the class. 2. Questions and tasks intended for the group. 3. Questions and tasks intended for individual students" [5; p. 54].

Prof. R. Niyozmetova's proposal, that is, these three groups of questions and assignments, can be based on the didactic part of "Literature" textbooks.

H. M. In his candidate work, Suyunov emphasized that the questions and assignments given to students in the lower and upper classes are different in order for the students to fully master the educational material given in the textbooks and textbooks-complexes: If questions and assignments are used, then in the upper grades, questions that rise to the title of independent work types such as abstract, essay, lecture text, and review are important," says [9; p. 96].

It is noteworthy that in today's methodology of literary education and the "State Standard of Literary Education" not only in the lower classes, but also in the literary education of the upper classes, knowledge of theoretical concepts such as "artistic plot", "composition", "conflict" is not required. In general, in "Literature" textbooks, questions and tasks related to the study of the writer's or poet's biography, works and their essence and genres should be prepared in such a way that the

student is not limited to reading sentences from the text when answering them. He is "forced" to express the answer to the question in his own words. Don't limit yourself to retelling the content of the text. Let him express his reaction to the events in the text. Before answering the questions, let the student repeatedly refer to the text, discuss and think. Let him try to put himself in the place of the hero. Let him compare it with himself and his friends. The structured questions help the reader to discover the charm of the literary text in many ways. It should not be overlooked that at the heart of the questions and assignments is not only the goal of checking the student, evaluating him, but also teaching him to discover the artistic text, work on the work, express the artistic pleasure and charm of the text in his own words, express an opinion about the work, and do independent research. Then the questions and assignments based on the texts will serve the purpose of teaching literature. A study of the psychological characteristics of 5th-7th graders showed that they have a strong tendency to compare. For this reason, it is necessary to pay attention to creating questions and assignments to compare the student with the hero of the work or the heroes of two works.

Today, one of the problems in the creation of "Literature" textbooks is the issue of the size of the textbooks. In this regard, Professor Q. In his answers to the questions of the reporter of the magazine "Yoshlik", Yoldoshev spoke about the size of the textbooks and said: "...Literature has reached such a level that the size of the textbook "Literature" for the ninth grade, where literature is taught three hours a week, is the size of the eighth, seventh, sixth, where the subject of literature is taught for two hours a week, even smaller than a fifth grade textbook. At a time when the whole society recognizes that the struggle for spirituality is a matter of life and death, the students of the graduating class are deprived of literature... There is no one who can eliminate such an irrational norm that teenagers in the ninth grade are assigned to carry less burden than teenagers in the fifth grade" [1; p. 148].

As long as it is necessary to limit the size of the textbooks, the gaps that may appear in literary education can be covered by separate "companion textbooks". In addition to the main textbook, such textbooks have the same columns as in the "Literature" textbooks, a wider sample of the works included in the textbook, samples of other works of the same authors, works of art recommended for independent study in the program, questions and tasks that check the student's knowledge after each topic, tests, visual arts. samples can be provided on a large scale.

In addition to these, there are also state education standards. In particular, the state standard for literary education sets the minimum level of students' knowledge, that is, the state claims the average of the knowledge given in literature classes. A student with average knowledge in literature classes can meet the requirements of DTS. The students whose knowledge exceeds these requirements, that is, who fully acquire the knowledge recommended in the program, and sometimes reach higher levels, will definitely be the future of the world of literature. It requires a lot of extra work from both the student and the teacher involved.

The main force that ensures effectiveness in teaching literature in schools is the personality of the teacher. In education, no matter how perfect and complete the curriculum is, programs and textbooks are multifaceted, works recommended for learning are impressive, no matter how strong the artistic appeal is, if it is not properly conveyed to the student, if it is not able to influence the spirituality of the student, all of them will remain ineffective on paper. The influence of the created didactic tools reaches the student only through the personality of the teacher, his outlook and work. A literature teacher must be a skilled performer. And for a skilled performer, quality training material is required. "The process of reading the literary text of the teacher determines the methods of teaching," says V. A. Kan-Kalik and V. I. Khazan [2; p. 148].

Another factor that determines the content of literature teaching at school is textbooks. "Methodical manuals are textbooks containing materials related to the methodology of teaching or educating a subject or a part of it, and it is written for teachers" [6; p. 4].

Methodical manuals for teaching literature based on today's requirements are available in the school, although there are few. That is, it was demanded to create a new generation of "Literature" textbooks together with methodological manuals in the form of a comprehensive educational-methodical complex (MMC). Their content is another matter. Apart from them, there are also small recommendations. Methodical articles published in the periodical press, especially in the "Language and Literature Education" magazine, constitute the majority, and they are an alternative to the "Teacher's book" which is similar in content to the textbooks.

In the recent past, there were a number of manuals, including additional materials for studying the personality and creativity of a writer or poet, which aspects of them, how to reveal their characteristics, how to study the work, how to study the work, the power of influence, and the effectiveness of it. Today, it is impossible to rely on many of them, of course. Because there is a big difference between the goals and tasks of literary education at that time and today. In this sense, creating various methodical manuals recommending different methods of learning works from textbooks, creating manuals that allow teachers to selectively use teaching methods is a requirement of the time.

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